

YIELD AND QUALITY PARAMETERS OF CUCUMBER AS INFLUENCED BY APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT PLASTIC MULCHES AND COW URINE

P.D. Maheta¹, B. M. Nandre², Yogesh Pawar³ and V. R. Wankhade⁴, Dhawani Patel⁵¹ P.G. student, Department of Vegetable Science, College of Horticulture, SDAU, Jagudan² Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture, SDAU, Tharad³ Scientist, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, SDAU, Deesa⁴ Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, C.P. College of Agriculture, SDAU, Sardarkrushinagar⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of Floriculture and Landscape Architecture, College of Horticulture, SDAU, Jagudanbmnandre@gmail.com

(MS Received: 23.11.2023; MS Revised: 29.12.2023; MS Accepted: 30.12.2023)

MS 3125

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE,)

Abstract

An experiment entitled, "yield and quality parameters of cucumber as influenced by application of different plastic mulches and cow urine" was conducted at College farm, College of Horticulture, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Jagudan, Dist. Mehsana during summer season of 2019 comprising of two factors viz. different plastic mulches (bare soil, black plastic mulch, silver plastic mulch, red plastic mulch) in main plot with four levels (control, 5% cow urine, 10% cow urine, 15% cow urine) in sub plot with four levels. The total sixteen combinations were tested in Split Plot Design with three replications. Observations were recorded on yield and quality parameters. Among the different types of plastic mulches, silver plastic mulches significantly increased number of fruits per vine (12.98), average fruit weight (140.68 g), yield per vine, yield per plot and yield per hectare (1.83 kg, 19.29 kg and 213.66 q, respectively) fruit length (17.98 cm) and fruit diameter (3.74 cm). Among the application of cow urine, 15% cow urine significantly increased number of fruits per vine (12.42), average fruit weight (143.12 g), yield per vine (1.78 kg), yield per plot (18.81 kg), yield per hectare (209.00 q), and total soluble solid (3.39 °Brix). Among treatments combination m_2c_3 (silver plastic mulch with 15% cow urine) proved superior in terms of yield and yield parameters.

Key words – cucumber, yield and quality, mulches and cow urine.

Introduction

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is one of the most popular and quickest maturing vine vegetable crops and is the second most widely cultivated cucurbit after watermelon. The immature fruits of cucumber are used as salad and for pickling. The fruits and seed possess cooling properties. The fruit is also used as an astringent and antipyretic. The seed oil is used as antipyretic. Fruits are good for people suffering from constipation, jaundice and indigestion. The nutritional composition of a 100 g portion of cucumber includes most of its weight in water with proteins, fat and carbohydrate as primary metabolites and also dietary fiber that is important for the digestive system. Nutritional composition of 100 g edible portion of cucumber fruit having water 96.4 g, energy 42 Kj (10 kcal), protein 7 g, fat 1 g, carbohydrate 1.5 g, dietary fiber 6 g, thiamin 0.03 mg, riboflavin 0.01 mg, niacin 0.2 mg and ascorbic acid 2 mg. Inorganic mulch induces plastic mulch and accounts for the greatest volume of mulch used in commercial crop production. The plastic material uses as mulch are polyvinyl chloride or polyethylene films. Owing to its greater permeability to long wave radiation it can increase temperature around the plants during night. Hence, polyethylene film mulch is preferred as mulching material for production of horticulture crops. LDPE (Low density polyethylene), HDPE (High density polyethylene) and flexible PVC have all been used for mulching. Today the vast majority of plastic mulch is based on LLDPE (Linear low-density polyethylene) because it is more economic in use. Now-a-days application of silver plastic mulch film is becoming popular and very good results have been achieved particularly in arid and semi-arid region. Silver polyethylene mulches are used for weed control in a range of crops under the organic system of crop production. White polyethylene mulch is use in warmer climates, heating the soil is not required and plants benefit from cooling the soil instead. Yellow polythene mulch attracts certain insects and thus acts as a trap for them, which prevents disease. Red polythene mulch partially translucent allowing radiation to pass through and warm soil but also reflect radiation back into plant canopy changing ratio of R:FR light, which result in changes in plant vegetative, flower development and metabolism to early fruiting and increased yield in some vegetable crops. Black polyethylene mulch is used to exclude light and due to lack of photosynthesis; weeds are suppressed. Cow urine has a unique place in Ayurveda and has been described in 'Sushruta Samhita' and 'Astanga Sangraha' to be the most effective substance of animal origin with innumerable therapeutic values. It is not only used for human health but also for animal health and plant

growth. Different Ayurvedic literatures have mentioned the properties and uses of cow urine for treatment of various diseases. Application of cow urine besides improving the soil texture and working as a plant hormone also been reported to correct the micro nutrient deficiency. Being organic in nature it is also likely increase the fertilizer use efficiency. Therefore, it seems that cow urine under livestock based integrated farming system has a great potential for use as a bio fertilizer in crop production both as soil application and foliar spray and it needs to be studied under existing climate. Keeping into consideration the above fact an investigation entitled, "yield and quality parameters of cucumber as influenced by application of different plastic mulches and cow urine" was taken.

Material And Methods

The present investigation was undertaken during summer season under field conditions at College farm, College of Horticulture, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Jagudan, Dist. Mehsana, Gujarat. This experiment was comprising of two factors viz. four levels of plastic mulches (m_0 -control, m_1 - black plastic mulch, m_2 -silver plastic mulch and m_3 -red plastic mulch) and application of cow urine (c_0 -0 % cow urine, c_1 -5 % cow urine, c_2 -10 % cow urine and c_3 -15 % cow urine) in Split Plot Design. Urine application was given at 20, 30 and 50 DAS. Irrigation was provided by drip irrigation system. Observations of yield and quality parameters statistical analyzed as per the methods described by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

Results And Discussion**Yield parameters (Table 1 and 2)****Number of fruits per vine**

Significantly maximum number of fruits (12.98) per vine was observed with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch) which was at par with (12.20) m_1 (black plastic mulch). Incorporation of mulches might have enhanced the nutrient and moisture availability, thereby, helped in improving the soil conditions for better plant growth, balanced C: N ratio and thus increased the synthesis of photosynthates, which could be the possible reasons for increasing the values of fruit character. Similar finding confirmed with Rao *et al.* (2017) and Dadheech *et al.* (2018) in watermelon.

Maximum number of fruits (12.42) per vine was found in c_3 (15% cow urine), which was at par with (12.17) c_2 (10% cow urine). As discussed earlier, cow urine provides nitrogen which is essential for crop growth (vine length, number of branches, number of fruits per plant. Our results corroborate the regards of Susila *et al.* (2012) in

watermelon, Khan *et al.* (2001) in *tinda* and Ranjan *et al.* (2019) in muskmelon.

Significantly maximum number of fruits per vine (13.72) recorded in the treatment combination of m_2c_3 which was at par with m_1c_3 , m_1c_2 and m_2c_2 . This mulch consistently increased higher fruit set compare to control. This might have been influenced by favorable soil temperature, moisture conditions, pest and disease control by silver plastic mulch and cow urine (15%) foliar spray of urine which contain 0.9- 1.2 % nitrogen and hormones like cytokinins and auxins to reduce the abscission and thus retaining the fruits per vine. These results are supported by the findings of Nayak *et al.* (2017) in pointed gourd.

Average fruit weight (g)

Significantly maximum fruit weight (140.68 g) per plant was observed with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch) which was at par with (138.94 g) m_1 (black plastic mulch). Incorporation of mulches might have enhanced the nutrient and moisture availability, thereby, helped in improving the soil conditions for better plant growth, balanced C:N ratio and thus increased the synthesis of photosynthates, which could be the possible reasons for increasing the values of fruit character. Silver plastic mulch induce early flowering by increasing water use efficiency and fertilizer use efficiency. It maximized fruit weight by proper movement of active food syntheses to sink (Singh *et al.* 2009). Similar finding confirmed with Rao *et al.* (2017) and Dadheech *et al.* (2018) in watermelon.

Maximum fruit weight (143.12 g) was found in c_3 (15% cow urine), which was at par with (139.36 g) c_2 (10% cow urine). Cow urine contents small amount of urea, calcium and manganese which fulfilled the nutritional requirement of crop and increased the fruit weight (Tambe *et al.*, 2015). These results are conformity with the finding of Chaudhari and Patel (2010) in mango and Tambe *et al.* (2015) in chilli.

Significantly maximum fruit weight (152.11 g) recorded in the treatment combination of m_2c_3 which was at par with m_2c_2 , m_1c_3 and m_1c_2 . It is due to mulch, which maximized fruit weight by proper movement of active food synthesis to sink and application of cow urine which presence of urea, calcium and manganese increasing fruit weight. These results are supported by the findings of Nayak *et al.* (2017) in pointed gourd.

Yield per vine (kg), per plot (kg) and per hectare (q)

The significantly maximum yield per vine (1.83 kg) was recorded with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch), which was statistically at par (1.71 kg) with treatment m_1 (black plastic mulch). The significantly maximum yield per vine (1.78 kg) was obtained with treatment c_3 (15% cow urine) which was at par with treatment c_2 (1.69 kg).

The significantly maximum yield per plot (19.23 kg) was obtained with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch) and treatment c_3 (15% cow urine) respectively, being at par (18.02 kg) with treatment m_1 (black plastic mulch) and treatment c_2 (17.93 kg) respectively.

The significantly maximum yield per hectare (213.66 q) was recorded with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch), being at par (200.22 q) with treatment m_1 (black plastic mulch). The increase in yield was attributed to the sufficient soil moisture in the root zone and minimized evaporation loss due to mulching. The extended retention of moisture and availability of moisture also leads to higher yield as compared to the control. The results are probative to the findings of Rao *et al.* (2017) and Dadheech *et al.* (2018) in watermelon and Awasthi *et al.*, (2022) in cucumber.

Table 3: Effect of different plastic mulches and application of cow urine on economics and benefit cost ratio

Treatments	Yield per hectare (q/ha)	Gross realization (/ha)	Total cost of cultivation (₹/ha)	Net return (₹/ha)	Benefit Cost Ratio
m_0c_0	151.55	151550.00	82813.00	68737.00	1.83
m_0c_1	154.00	154000.00	84842.50	69157.50	1.82
m_0c_2	157.66	157660.00	84928.00	72732.00	1.86
m_0c_3	161.33	161330.00	85013.50	76316.50	1.90
m_1c_0	156.33	156330.00	94273.00	62057.00	1.66

The significantly maximum yield per hectare (209.00 q) was recorded with treatment c_3 (15% cow urine) which was statically at par (199.22 q) with treatment c_2 (10% cow urine) from the present study, 15% cow urine concentration was noted highest yield of fruits per vine (kg/plant) then other concentrations. According to Chaudhari and Shinde (2017) cow urine use as bio fertilizer and it is rich in source of macro and micro nutrients which improves the crop the crop productivity. Our result corroborates the finding of earlier refers Khanal *et al.* (2011) in cauliflower, Schmidt *et al.* (2015) in pumpkin. Significantly maximum yield per vine (2.09 kg), per plot (21.95 kg) and per hectare (243.88 q) was recorded in treatment combination of m_2c_3 (silver plastic mulch+15% cow urine). This was statistically at par with m_2c_2 , m_1c_3 and m_1c_2 . The results due to silver plastic mulch which altering evapotranspiration and increased root growth by favorable soil temperature and increasing photosynthetic rate through increased irradiance in the plant canopy, according to Chaudhari and Shinde (2017). Cow urine use as bio fertilizer and it is rich in source of macro and micro nutrients which improves the crop the crop productivity. These results are supported by the findings of Nayak *et al.* (2017) in pointed gourd.

Quality parameters (Table 1 and 2)

Fruit length (cm)

Significantly maximum fruit length (17.98 cm) was observed with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch) which was at par with (17.60 cm) m_1 (black plastic mulch). Due to congenial soil moisture result higher uptake of nutrition for better growth of fruit and the reduction in evaporation losses of soil moisture caused by mulches covered the soil surface. These findings are in accordance with findings of Rathava *et al.* (2012), Parmar *et al.* (2013) and Dadheech *et al.* (2018) in watermelon.

Fruit diameter (cm)

Significantly maximum fruit diameter (3.74 cm) was observed with treatment m_2 (silver plastic mulch) which was at par with (3.64 cm) m_1 (black plastic mulch). Due to congenial soil moisture result higher uptake of nutrition for better growth of fruit and the reduction in evaporation losses of soil moisture caused by mulches covered the soil surface. These findings are in accordance with findings of Rathava *et al.* (2012), Parmar *et al.* (2013) and Dadheech *et al.* (2018) in watermelon.

Total soluble solid (°Brix)

Influence of different plastic mulches on total soluble solid was found non- significant. Maximum total soluble solid (3.40°Brix) was found in c_3 (15% cow urine). Which was at par with (3.27 °Brix) c_2 (10% cow urine). Due to presence of efficient water, N, P, K, micronutrients cow urine treatments give better quality parameters. These results are conformity with the finding of Misra *et al.* (2007) in asparagus and Chaudhari and Patel (2010) in mango.

Ascorbic acid (mg/100)

Ascorbic acid was non-significantly influenced in different plastic mulches, application of cow urine and its interaction.

Economics

Influence of different plastic mulches and application of cow urine on net return and benefit cost ratio in cucumber are presented in Table 3. Application of treatment m_3c_2 (Silver plastic mulch + 15% cow urine) recorded maximum gross return (₹ 243880.00), net return (₹ 147406.50) and cost: benefit ratio (1:2.53).

m ₁ c ₁	180.88	180880.00	96302.50	84577.50	1.88
m ₁ c ₂	232.22	232220.00	96388.00	135832.00	2.41
m ₁ c ₃	241.44	241440.00	96473.50	144966.50	2.50
m ₂ c ₀	184.33	184330.00	94273.00	90057.00	1.96
m ₂ c ₁	184.33	184330.00	96302.50	88027.50	1.91
m ₂ c ₂	242.26	242260.00	96388.00	145872.00	2.51
m ₂ c ₃	243.88	243880.00	96473.50	147406.50	2.53
m ₃ c ₀	163.77	163770.00	94273.00	69497.00	1.74
m ₃ c ₁	167.44	167440.00	96302.50	71137.50	1.74
m ₃ c ₂	171.11	171110.00	96388.00	74722.00	1.78
m ₃ c ₃	199.22	199220.00	96473.50	102746.50	2.07

Conclusion

It may be conducted that summer cucumber plant mulched with silver plastic mulch and application of 15 % cow urine was most remunerative and beneficial.

References

1. **Awasthi, P.; Bogati, S.; Shah, P.; Joshi, D.; Adhikari, S.; Bohara, S. S.; Banjade, D. and Malla, S. (2022).** Effect of different mulching materials on growth and yield of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* cv. Bhaktapur local), in Gokuleshwor, Baitadi. *Tropical Agrobiodiversity*. **3**(2): 30-35.
2. **Chaudhari, P. and Patel, B. (2010).** Effect of pre-sowing treatment, sowing position and duration on germination of mango stones. *Bioinfolet- A Quarterly Journal of Life Science*. **9**(3): 277-279.
3. **Chaudhari, T. and Shinde, V. (2017).** Effect of water, cow dung slurry and cow urine on Mango (*Mangifera indica*L.) stones cv. Rajapuri. *International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. **4**(2): 425-431.
4. **Dadheech, S.; Ramawtar and Yadav, C. (2018).** Impact of mulching material on the growth, yield and quality of watermelon (*Citrulluslanatus*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Science*. **7**: 2319-7706.
5. **Khan, A.; Iqbal, M.; Muhammad, S.; Ghaffore, A. and Waseem, K. (2001).** Effect of different sowing dates on the yield of Tinda Gourd (*Citrullus vulgaris*) Var. Fidulosus under the agro climatic conditions. *Online journal of biological Sciences*. **1**(4): 235-237.
6. **Khanal, A.; Shakya, S. and Sharma, M. (2011).** Utilization of urine waste to produce quality cauliflower. *The Journal of Agriculture and Environment*. **12**: 91-96.
7. **Misra, H. R.; Mahorkar, V. K.; Jadhao, B. J. and Nandre D. R. (2007).** Effect of micronutrients and humic acid on growth and leaf yield of asparagus. *Plant Archives*. **7**(1):321-322.
8. **Nayak, H. (2017).** Effect of fertigation and mulching on growth yield and shelf life of Pointed Gourd (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.) cv. Swarna Alaukik. *Scientia Horticultural*. **6**(2):117-123.
9. **Panse, V. G. and Sukhatme, P. V. (1985).** Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers. 4thEdn., Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), New Delhi.

10. **Parmar, H.N.; Polara, N. D. and Viradiya, R.R. (2013).** Effect of mulching material on growth, yield and Quality of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb) cv. Kiran. *Univ. J. Agric. Res.***1**: 30-37. 2013.
11. **Ranjan, A.; Kumar, A.; Prakash, S. and Pal, A. (2019).** Effect of low poly tunnel and planting time on growth parameters and yield of muskmelon. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*. **8**(1): 2735-2739.
12. **Rao, K. V. R.; Bajpai, A.; Gangwar S.; Chourasia L. and Soni, K. (2017).**Effect of mulching on growth, yield and economics of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb). *Environment & Ecology***35**(3): 2437-2441.
13. **Rathava, V. D.; Patel, M. C.; Vadodaria, J. R.; Vasava, H. V. and Pawar, Y. D. (2015).** Revolutionary performance of mulches on morphological, quantitative and qualitative attributes of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) cv. Asahi Yamato. *Green Farming*.**6**(5): 1162-1164.
14. **Schmidt, H.; Pandit, B.; Martinsen, V.; Cornelissen, G.; Conte, P. and Kammann, C. (2015).** Fourfold increase in pumpkin yield in response to low-dosage root zone application of urine-enhanced biochar to a fertile tropical soil. *The Journal of Agriculture*.**5**:723-741.
15. **Singh, Y. M.; Reddy, M. S and Bajpai, K.V. (2009)** Effect of different biodegradable and plastic mulches on soil properties and production on a tomato crop. *Sci, Horti*.**109**(2): 216-224.
16. **Susila, T.; Reddy, S.; Rajkumar, M.; Padmaja, G. and Rao, P. (2012).** Effect of sowing date and spraying of brassinosteroid on yield and fruit quality characters of watermelon. *World journal of Agricultural Sciences*. **8**(3): 223-228.
17. **Taber, H. (2002).** Selection of plastic mulch for early muskmelon production. *Scientia Horticultural*. **6**(2):117-123.
18. **Tambe, A.; Dhawan, A. and Gourkhede, P. (2015).** Studies on yield and quality improvement of chilli through organic nutrition. *National Academy of Agriculture Science*. **33**(4): 3765-3770.

Table 1: Effect of different plastic mulches and application of cow urine on yield and quality of cucumber

Treatments	Number of fruits per vine	Average fruit weight (g)	Yield			Fruit length (cm)	Fruit diameter (cm)	TSS (°B)	Ascorbic acid (mg/100)
			Per vine (kg)	Per plot (kg)	Per hectare (q)				
Mulches (M)									
m₀	9.82	130.20	1.28	14.06	156.22	14.45	3.36	3.12	9.15
m₁	12.20	138.94	1.71	18.02	200.22	17.60	3.64	3.27	9.03
m₂	12.98	140.68	1.83	19.23	213.66	17.98	3.74	3.40	8.87
m₃	10.85	131.65	1.44	15.07	167.44	15.15	3.45	3.27	8.94
S. Em. ±	0.40	2.36	0.06	0.60	6.71	0.35	0.08	0.05	0.11
C. D. at 5%	1.40	8.17	0.20	2.09	23.22	1.21	0.28	NS	NS
C. V. %	12.23	6.05	12.53	12.53	12.53	7.40	7.75	6.06	4.12
Cow Urine (C)									
c₀	10.52	129.37	1.34	14.38	159.77	15.79	3.43	3.16	9.02
c₁	11.25	129.62	1.44	15.26	169.55	16.13	3.51	3.23	9.17
c₂	12.17	139.36	1.69	17.93	199.22	16.52	3.58	3.29	8.81
c₃	12.42	143.12	1.78	18.81	209.00	16.79	3.67	3.39	9.00
S. Em. ±	0.25	2.12	0.04	0.42	4.78	16.95	0.07	0.05	0.08
C. D. at 5%	0.72	6.19	0.12	1.24	13.85	NS	NS	0.15	NS
Interaction									
S. Em. ±	0.49	4.24	0.08	0.85	9.49	0.63	0.14	0.10	0.17
C. D. at 5%	1.43	12.39	0.24	2.49	27.70	NS	NS	NS	NS
C. V. %	7.42	5.43	9.02	9.02	9.02	6.63	6.86	5.58	3.34

Table 2: Interaction effect of plastic mulches and cow urine on yield and quality

Treatments	Number of fruits per vine	Average fruit weight (g)	Yield		
			Per vine (kg)	Per plot (kg)	Per hectare (q)
m0c0	9.66	128.09	1.24	13.64	151.55
m0c1	9.67	129.10	1.26	13.84	153.77
m0c2	9.95	130.24	1.29	14.17	157.44
m0c3	10.01	131.39	1.32	14.49	161.00
m1c0	10.40	129.24	1.34	14.05	156.11
m1c1	12.02	132.53	1.55	16.24	180.44
m1c2	13.69	146.06	1.99	20.90	232.22
m1c3	13.71	150.92	2.07	21.70	241.11
m2c0	12.24	129.38	1.57	16.55	183.88
m2c1	12.27	129.18	1.58	16.57	184.11
m2c2	13.68	152.06	2.08	21.81	242.33
m2c3	13.72	152.11	2.09	21.95	243.88
m3c0	10.29	129.76	1.34	14.71	163.44
m3c1	10.52	129.68	1.37	15.07	167.44
m3c2	10.87	129.06	1.40	15.43	171.44
m3c3	11.72	138.12	1.63	17.90	198.88
S. Em. ±	0.49	4.24	0.08	0.85	9.49
C. D. at 5%	1.43	12.39	0.24	2.49	27.70
C. V. %	7.42	5.43	9.02	9.02	9.02